

New information about *Cyclophora pupillaria* (HÜBNER, 1799) (Lepidoptera: Geometridae) and recent records from Poland

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ABSTRACT. New information about *Cyclophora pupillaria* (HÜBNER, 1799) (Lepidoptera: Geometridae) and recent records from Poland.

New records of *Cyclophora pupillaria* (HÜBNER, 1799) (Geometridae) from western and south-eastern Poland are given. Its reappearance in Poland after more than 50 years is thought to be part of a more intensive migration trend involving this species in Europe at the present time. Cases of this species' migration in some western European countries from the same period as our records are cited.

KEY WORDS: Lepidoptera, Geometridae, faunistics, new records, Poland, *Cyclophora pupillaria*.

INTRODUCTION

Migration is not uncommon in some lepidopteran families: it is very frequent in sphingid and noctuid moths (EITSCHBERGER *et al.* 1991), but not among geometrids. These latter moths rarely undertake migration flights and then only over relatively short distances, possibly because of their delicate body structure. But there are exceptions, one of which is *Cyclophora pupillaria* (HÜBNER, 1799), known for its annual long-distance migration flights (HAUSMANN 2004). This species has a widespread distribution in southern Europe, in the Mediterranean and Black Sea Basins, and in the Balkans, reaching as far north as southern and western Hungary and the borderlands with Slovakia. It has turned up occasionally in central Europe: Austria, Switzerland, Germany, Denmark, the Netherlands, Belgium, Ukraine and Slovakia (HAUSMANN 2004), in western Russia (MIRONOV *et al.* 2008) and more recently in the Czech Republic (JIRGL 2015, LAŠTŮVKA *et al.* 2017). It has also penetrated as far as Sweden, Great Britain and Ireland (SKINNER 1984). From the German Länder bordering on Poland there is the only record of the single individual (Einzelfund) from Brandenburg in the period 1981-2000 (GAEDICKE *et al.* 2017). In Poland, this species was discovered 23 years ago in Stanisław Batkowski's collection of Lepidoptera, deposited in the Tatra Museum in Zakopane. This was a series of 5 individuals attracted to light on the Gubałówka hill above Zakopane (UTM: DV26) in 1961 – 1 ex., 1966 – 3 exx. and 1967 – 1 ex. (leg. S. Batkowski). At that time, all were identified and described as a species new to Poland (MALKIEWICZ 1998). Subsequent years brought no new reports of this species from anywhere in Poland.

The Distributional Checklist of the Lepidoptera of Poland (MALKIEWICZ 2017) lists *C. pupillaria* from the provinces of Podkarpacie (SE Poland) and Wielkopolska (W Poland) on the basis of the previously unpublished records cited in this article.

METHODS AND RESULTS

Cyclophora pupillaria (HÜBNER, 1799) (Fig. 1) was caught during fieldwork at two localities in the provinces of Podkarpacie and Wielkopolska. These are new records of this species following a hiatus of more than 50 years.

Poland:

Podkarpacie: Rzepedź, Bieszczady Mts. (UTM: EV87), 8 VII 2013 – 1 ♂, caught at light, (250 W mercury vapour lamp), leg. F. Paluch, det. A. Malkiewicz & M. Hołowiński;

Wielkopolska: Poznań, Morasko (UTM: XU21), 13 X 2014 – 1 ♂, caught at light (500 W mercury vapour lamp), leg. Ł. Matuszewski, det. A. Malkiewicz & Ł. Matuszewski.

In the context of this discovery, we analysed the migration events of this species in central and western Europe on the basis of available data from the same periods. We took into account reports in scientific publications and entries in faunistics databases in a number of European countries where this species is regarded as a migrant. Our analysis did not include the countries that lie within its continuous distribution.

Below we cite records of *C. pupillaria* from other countries in 2013–2014:

Czech Republic:

Káraný, 17 X 2014 (Jirgl 2015; LAŠTŮVKA *et al.* 2017).

Belgium:

Seen at four localities in East Flanders in 2013 and 2014.

Wondelgem (OV) near Ghent: 18 VII 2013 – 1 ex., 19 VII 2013 – 1 ex., 21 IX 2014 – 2 exx. (www.warnemingen.be);

Vinderhout – Cohousing: 9 VIII 2013 – 1 ex., 10 VIII 2013 – 1 ex. (www.warnemingen.be);

Merendree – Durmen: 6 IX 2013 – 1 ex., 8 IX 2013 – 1 ex. (www.warnemingen.be);

Belzele – Ralingen: 8 IX 2013 – 1 ex. (www.warnemingen.be).

The Netherlands:

Biggekerkein, province of Zeeland (Holland): 30 X 2014 – 1 ex. (www.vlinderstichting.nl).

Local observers are of the opinion that a stable, local population has established itself on the western periphery of Ghent, which indicates that *C. pupillaria* can also occur (at least periodically) as a sedentary moth in Belgium. Following the first record in the garden of Mr D. De Vreeze in Wondelgem on 18 July 2013, eight further records were obtained in the near vicinity (www.warnemingen.be).

Great Britain:

Dorset: 18 X 2013 – 12 exx. (www.dorsetmothgroup.info/portal);

Notfield, Surrey: 7 IX 2014 – 1 ex (GBIF);

Dorset: 5 IX - 31 X 2014 – 3 exx. (www.dorsetmothgroup.info/portal);

Long Avenue, Clevedon (Wales): 16 X 2014 – 1 ex. (GBIF).

DISCUSSION

The incidental reappearance of *C. puppillaria* in Poland provides confirmation of this species' periodic migrations into the more northerly regions of Europe. Besides the Polish record from 2014, information was published on the trapping of one individual of this moth in the Czech Republic during the same period of the year (13-19 X 2014). This was the first and to date sole record of *C. puppillaria* in that country (JIRGL 2015). From that same period there are also records from the Benelux countries and Great Britain, where lepidopterans have been regularly and intensively monitored for many years, the records being published in on-line databases. The number of records from 2013 and 2014 show that the migrations of this moth in central and western Europe are intensifying. However, there are no more recent indications that *C. puppillaria* has been migrating across our part of the continent. But based on later records from Great Britain and Denmark (GBIF), researchers there have set up the hypothesis that, as a result of multiple migrations, propitious weather conditions like warm winters, and an abundance of its food plants, *C. puppillaria* is forming local, periodically stable populations in Great Britain (CLANCY 2014, www.hantsmoths.org.uk).

It is not unlikely that these populations are being supplemented by individuals arriving from the south during the species' annual migrations (BUTTER *et al.* 2020). Even so, there are no unequivocal data confirming the origin of the moths in these local populations in the Benelux countries and Great Britain. British entomologists consider that this species is a migrant from continental Europe, turning up ever more frequently in southern England. The numbers of records in Hampshire and the Isle of Wight have increased very considerably, from 10-20 per year in 2006-2012 (compared with around 30 in the previous 60 years or so) to more than 200 in 2018 alone (LESLIE J. EVANS-HILL 2014).

The existence of stable, local populations of *C. puppillaria* in Poland or indeed anywhere else in central Europe seems rather unlikely as most of its food plants do not grow there (evergreen oaks *Quercus*, *Cistus*, *Myrtus*, *Erica* and *Arbutus unedo*). From the available faunistics information one may infer that in favourable weather conditions, these moths regularly attempt to colonize new environments during their cyclic migrations. But only under very propitious circumstances, such as prevailed in 2013-2014, can these attempts succeed, not only in western but also central Europe, including Poland. Neither in the years before that period nor subsequently has *C. puppillaria* been recorded in our part of Europe – at least there is no published information confirming such occurrences. It is, however, an ever more frequent visitor to western Europe, possibly forming periodically localized populations, such as in Great Britain and the Benelux countries. Exceptionally mild winters and global warming are probably responsible for these migrations and colonization attempts.

The voucher specimens are deposited in the collections of Łukasz Matuszewski and Filip Paluch.

Fig. 1. *Cyclophora puppillaria* (HÜBNER, 1799) from Poznań-Morasko (XU21), Poland – colour form with reduced pattern of the wings, excluding cell rings at both wings and medial fascia at hindwings.

Ryc. 1. *Cyclophora puppillaria* (HÜBNER, 1799) z Poznania-Morasko (XU21), Polska – forma barwna ze zredukowanym wzorem skrzydeł, zanikiem plamki środkowej na obu skrzydłach i cienia środkowego na tylnych skrzydłach.

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STRESZCZENIE

Uzupełnienie wiedzy na temat występowania *Cyclophora pupillaria* (HÜBNER, 1799) (Lepidoptera: Geometridae) oraz nowe dane o występowaniu tego gatunku w Polsce

Podano nowe wzmianki o *Cyclophora pupillaria* (HÜBNER, 1799) (Geometridae) z zachodniej i południowo-wschodniej Polski. Uważa się, że jego ponowne pojawienie się w Polsce po ponad 50 latach jest częścią intensywniejszego trendu migracji tego gatunku w Europie w omawianym okresie. Zacytowane są przypadki migracji tego gatunku w niektórych krajach Europy Zachodniej z tego samego okresu, w którym są podawane nasze rekordy. W pracy dyskutowane jest znaczenie warunków atmosferycznych i anomalii klimatycznych dla tego typu epizodów migracyjnych.

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